

PRO-PV LOCAL BUILDING POLICY – STATE OF PROGRESS OF THE LYON-CONFLUENCE SOLAR CITY PROJECT

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ABSTRACT: Following the conclusions of the successful task on Urban scale PV systems (Task 10) of the Photovoltaic Power System Program (PVPS) of the International Energy Agency (IEA), a pro-PV local building policy has been set-up for the purpose of the Lyon-Confluence urban project, a 150 ha redevelopment in the city center of Lyon, France, in order to make real-estate developers and architects design and build low energy buildings equipped with PV systems. This pro-PV local building policy was first tested in 2004 within the EC funded CONCERTO initiative by SPL Lyon-Confluence, the public company in charge of this redevelopment, for the construction of the first dwellings and office spaces of the area (A, B and C blocks). Now, with 10 blocks of the Lyon-Confluence area already equipped with one or several PV systems for a total power of 1.1 MW, this pro-PV local building policy has been improved and the use of PV will increase with more and larger systems. Thus, 6 other buildings will soon be equipped with PV systems for an additional power of more 1,2 MWp that will make the Lyon-Confluence area a significant solar city showcase.

Keywords: PV Market, Solar Architecture, Building Integrated PV (BIPV), R&D and Demonstration Programmes

1 THE SOLAR CITY CONCEPT

The concept of solar city was addressed in detail from 2004 to 2009 by experts from many countries involved in Task 10 of the Photovoltaic Power System Program (PVPS) of the International Energy Agency (IEA) related to Urban Scale PV applications [1].

Conclusions of the IEA PVPS Task 10 have been summarized in a book published in 2009 [2] with a detailed analysis of success factors and potential problems of urban-scale PV systems, based on the feedback from urban areas where the installation of significant amounts of PV had been completed or was planned. In all of the areas reviewed in this book the quantity of PV is significant, impacting substantially on the area where it is located. This is the case for instance of two major urban projects in the Netherlands both of which are considered to be worldwide best practices:

- The Waterkwartier district of the Nieuwland expansion area of the city of Amersfoort completed in 1999 (1 MW),
- The 'City of the Sun' in Heerhugowaard, Alkmaar and Langedijk completed in 2009 (5 MW).

Figure 1: The 'City of the Sun' in Heerhugowaard, in the Netherlands built in 2009 (5 MW)

Such world best practices have been used as background for the specification of the Lyon-Confluence urban project.

2 THE LYON-CONFLUENCE URBAN PROJECT

The goal of the Lyon-Confluence project is to redevelop a former industrial area of 150 ha in the city center of Lyon and to build 1.000.000 m² of new dwellings, offices and shops by 2030 [3]. The district is divided into 3 different areas:

- An area of 74 ha with 600.000 m² of existing buildings called "Sainte-Blandine" (green area below),
- 400.000 m² of new buildings built from 2003 to 2016 on 41 ha in the western part, near the Saone river (ZAC 1 - red area below),
- 400.000 m² of new buildings to be built from 2016 to 2030 on 35 ha in the eastern part near the Rhône river (ZAC 2 - blue area below).

Figure 2: Site plan of Lyon-Confluence with the existing area (in green) and the 2 new areas (in red and blue).

On top of this global objective, this project has very ambitious targets in terms of sustainability that are described in a Sustainable Action Plan design with WWF[4]. One of the most ambitious goals set in this action plan is the Zero Carbon objective defined as follow: the 1 million m² of floor area of new buildings to be built in the area by 2030 should not lead to any increase of the CO₂ emissions of the area.

In order to reach this goal, SPL Lyon-Confluence, the public company in charge of the redevelopment of the area, has undertaken several concrete measures to:

- Drastically reduce the consumption of new buildings in the area,
- Refurbish the existing buildings of the Perrache/Sainte-Blandine district located in the north of the area,
- Massively install, on almost each new block, renewable energy systems such as wood chip boilers, solar thermal systems and PV systems.

This article provides information on the tasks undertaken by SPL Lyon-Confluence to make PV systems installed in this area by third parties such as real estate developers.

2 FIRST PV SYSTEMS IN THE AREA

In 2004, SPL Lyon-Confluence launched an international competition for the construction of the first 3 blocks of the area for a total of approx. 80.000 m² composed of dwellings, offices and shops (A, B and C blocks). For the first time in France, this international design competition included a section on energy efficiency and renewable energy systems. The environmental engineering office TRIBU defined the environmental and energy targets of this group of buildings:

- Consumption for heating and domestic hot water under 60 kWh/m²/year,
- 80% of the consumption provided by renewable energy systems.

At that time this was less than 50% of the energy limit than written in the national thermal regulations and was made possible with the financial support of the European Commission within the CONCERTO initiative (€4 million of funding provided) [5].

Three real-estate developers associated with world-class architects such as Massimiliano Fuksas, MVRDV and Tania Concko were selected to build these first blocks. These real-estate developers had to comply with the local building regulations set out by SPL Lyon-Confluence and build efficient buildings powered mainly by renewable energy systems: wood chip boilers, solar thermal systems and also PV systems (see table I and figure 3).

Table I: features of renewable energy systems installed on the first building blocks of the area

	A Block	B Block	C Block
Wood boilers (kW)	540	2x540	540
Solar thermal systems (m ²)	-	240	250
PV systems (kWp)	79	121	65

Figure 3: Architecturally integrated PV systems of A block (79 kWp)

This demonstration project had a significant effect on other new buildings built in the area since several real-estate developers choose to install PV systems on their buildings despite not being obliged to and not receiving specific subsidies.

3 PV POTENTIAL OF THE AREA

In order to understand how much PV could be installed on existing buildings of the area, SPL Lyon-Confluence undertook, in 2009, a PV potential study, a first of its kind in France. The main deliverable of this PV potential study was a solar cadaster of the area designed in partnership with other experts from Europe within the EC funded POLIS project [6].

Figure 4: Map of the area with PV potential in kWp for the existing building stock (colour code: the darker the more share of the roof can be used)

The PV potential study concluded that most of the housing blocks were not suited for the installation of PV systems due to the complex decision making process of jointly-owned buildings and the small size of each PV system. However the study concluded that 1,2 MW of PV could be easily installed on 8 existing public buildings such as primary schools, high schools and sports halls. The PV potential study led to the fostering of several PV projects, such as the one on the gymnasium currently under design (206 kWp).

4 POSITIVE ENERGY BUILDINGS

In 2011, SPL Lyon-Confluence decided to go a step further and to launch an international design competition for the construction of a 12.300 m² positive energy building on a 3.400 m² piece of land called P plot. The team Bouygues Immobilier/SLC (real-estate developer) in association with Kengo Kuma from Japan (architect) was selected by the jury for the construction of this group of 3 buildings called HAKARI, with dwellings, offices places and shops. In order to build a positive energy building to respect the requirements set out by SPL Lyon-Confluence, the selected team decided to equip this building with 2 kinds of PV systems: a see-through PV facade on the building located in the middle of the block (21 kWp) and a rooftop PV system on the roof of each of the 3 buildings (168 kWp) [7]. The official opening ceremony of this building took place on Thursday 17 September 2015.

Figure 5: HIKARI, a positive energy building with a PV façade (21 kWp) and a rooftop PV system (168 kWp)

This demonstration project was also judged successful and the positive energy requirements set by SPL Lyon-Confluence for this block has been replicated to future blocks of the area.

4 PV SYSTEMS UNDER DESIGN

At the time of writing, 6 new PV systems for a total of 1,2 MWp are under design. Two of these should be installed on existing buildings as a direct result of the PV potential study undertaken in 2009:

- A 206 kWp PV system on the flat roof a gymnasium (see figure 6),
- A 250 kWp PV system on the sloped roof of an office building that will be dedicated to French Tech companies. For this project, a specific study is underway within the new Horizon 2020 Smart Cities and Communities program [8] to check if self-consumption of the energy produced could be a new business model for the operation of PV systems.

Also, there are in this area 2 new blocks under construction with the same energy performance requirements as the HIKARI buildings, i.e. positive energy buildings, on which architecturally integrated PV systems are planned:

- A 427 kWp system for the A3 block (28.000 m²) called – Ynfluence and built by ICADE,
- A 250 kWp system for the B2 block (12.000 m²) built by OGIC (see figure 7).

Figure 6: future PV system of the gymnasium (206 kWp)

Figure 7: artist impression of future PV system of the B2 block (250 kWp)

5 SUMMARY OF THE STATE OF PROGRESS AND PERSPECTIVE

Today, as a direct outcome of the pro-PV local building policy set up by SPL Lyon-Confluence, 10 blocks of the Lyon-Confluence area already equipped with one or several PV systems for a total power of 1.1 MW. Also, thanks to the improvement of this local policy that now requires real-estate developers to design and build positive energy buildings, and building on other local initiatives, 6 additional PV systems for a total of 1,2 MWp are currently under design. Thus, as the realistic PV potential of the area is assessed at 6,8 MW, the total PV power in this area will reach 2,2 MW once these PV systems are installed, one third of the total potential will be reached (see figure 8)

Figure 8: installed, planned and potential of PV systems in the Lyon-Confluence area

Lyon-Confluence become a significant solar city showcase, in the same way as the government district in Berlin, Germany, the Nieuwland project and the ‘City of the Sun’ project in the Netherlands.

Figure 8: Site plan of the Lyon-Confluence area with existing PV systems and PV systems under design

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